

Studies on Chelation of Humic Acid with Some Polyvalent Metal Ions

M. ADHIKARI, K. K. CHAKRABARTI and G. CHAKRABARTI

Physical Chemistry Laboratory,

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University.

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Investigations were made on interaction between certain bi, tri, tetra and hexa valent metallic cations with humic acid fraction isolated from alluvial soil of West Bengal by electrometric titrations and magnetic measurements. Electrometric titrations showed the formation of more than one chelates in each case and magnetic studies threw some light on the nature of the same.

THE stable complex formation of naturally occurring polyelectrolytes in soil, i.e. humic and fulvic acids with lower valent metal cations has been demonstrated by several workers^{1,2}. These weakly acidic polyelectrolytes play a prominent role in the binding of micronutrients in soil and in determining the fate of toxic heavy metal pollutants in the environment³. It is now believed that ion exchange, surface adsorption, chelation, coagulation and peptization processes are involved in such interactions^{4,5,6}. In the present paper attempt has been made to find out the nature of interactions of humic acid (HA) with some polyvalent cations, e.g., V⁺⁴, Ti⁺⁴, Mo⁺⁶, Fe⁺², Cu⁺² and Al⁺³.

Experimental

Humic acid (HA) used in the investigation has been extracted and fractionated from Bigra Pond sediment (Burdwan), West Bengal by the standard method as stated earlier⁷. The HA fraction has been subjected to repeated resin (IR-120) treatment to decrease the ash content to the minimum (0.01%) in order to get sure that the ligand is free from metal ions.

For conductometric and potentiometric titrations the procedure as discussed in earlier paper⁸ has been followed. The magnetic moments have been calculated from magnetic susceptibility measurement according to standard procedure⁹.

Results and Discussion

The average molecular weight of HA as measured by electrometric method¹⁰ has been found to be 2000. In the present discussion, the results are expressed on this basis.

Conductometric titrations

Instantaneous conductometric titration curves (Curves not shown here) are continuous in nature indicating no complex formation. But on allowing

the reaction mixture to equilibrate for 24 hours, two breaks are noticed in each case of HA-V⁺⁴, HA-Ti⁺⁴, HA-Mo⁺⁶ and HA-Fe⁺² combinations and one in each case of HA-Cu⁺² and HA-Al⁺³ combinations. The molal compositions corresponding to these inflexion points are 1:6 and 1:8 for HA:Fe⁺², 1:3 and 1:5 for HA:V⁺⁴, 1:2 and 1:4 for Ti⁺⁴, 1:3 and 1:6 for HA:Mo⁺⁶, 1:8 for HA:Cu⁺² and 1:1 for HA:Al⁺³.

During the titration of HA with Fe⁺², Cu⁺², Mo⁺⁶, V⁺⁴, Ti⁺⁴ and Al⁺³ cations conductances of the solutions increase after the formation of complexes. This is due to the fact that on interaction with metal cations highly conducting ionic species are resulted due to complex formation. Not only a strong electrolyte is produced from a weak electrolyte, but one of the ions formed is highly mobile, e.g., H⁺. The sharp rise in conductance after the formation of the complex is thus due to the liberation of such mobile hydrogen ions to form hydroxylated metal-HA complexes. During the titration with NaOH solution the initial conductance of different metal-HA combinations are greater than HA alone. It may possibly be due to weak acidic nature of HA having very low degree of ionisation. On interaction with metal ions the conductances increase considerably due to formation of strong electrolyte and subsequent liberation of hydrogen ions.

Furthermore, the conductance difference between the curves increases as the solution becomes more alkaline indicating that the complexes are more stable in basic media. The fact that titration with NaOH resulting in a low conductance when the chelate is formed may be visualised from the following reactions—

The large MA_n would be expected to have a lower conductance than the smaller anion A⁻ since the

latter is extensively hydrolysed in an aqueous solution to give the highly conducting ions.

Potentiometric titrations

Titration curves (not shown here) of organic ligand in presence of metal salts show considerable drop in pH. Although some lowering in pH may be expected due to acidifying effects of the salts; experiments carried out in absence of humic acid showed that for the concentration of salts used such a drop in pH cannot be accounted for. One possibility is that H⁺ ions are released from an otherwise non-titrable functional groups of HA (e.g., phenolic OH)¹⁴. Such a drop in pH by the addition of metal salts of HA solution varies markedly with the metal ions. Martell and Calvin¹¹ point out that greater the tendency of metals to combine with a given chelating agent greater is the pH drop. From the present study it is noted that complexing tendency of the metal ions with HA follows the order

From titration curves of HA with NaOH no second ionisation of weaker acidic groups has been noticed but in presence of different metal ions such ionisations are prominent. It is evident that the weaker acidic groups like phenolic hydroxyls take part in reaction with metal ions producing free hydrogen ions. As more and more such groups interact with metal ions, possibility of HA-metal complexes increases¹² followed by marked pH change. As according to Wood¹² et al, some of the COOH groups HA occupy adjacent sites on aromatic rings, it is logical to assume that the mode of metal-HA interaction may be of the phthalic acid type.

In order to get an idea about the mechanism of metal-HA interactions, the number of protons released by NaOH during the titration of HA and HA-metal mixtures are assessed in Tables 1(a) and 1(b).

TABLE-1(a)

pH	Number of protons released from HA/mole of base added
6.5	-
7.0	1.3
7.5	2.1
8.0	2.6
8.5	3.5
9.0	5.2

TABLE-1(b) NUMBER OF PROTONS RELEASED FROM HA/MOLE OF METAL ADDED

pH	HA : Fe ⁺²		HA : V ⁺⁴		HA : Ti ⁺⁴		HA : Mo ⁺⁶		HA : Cu ⁺²		HA : Al ⁺³
	(1:6)	(1:8)	(1:3)	(1:5)	(1:2)	(1:4)	(1:3)	(1:6)	(1:8)	(1:1)	
6.0	0.3	0.4	0.8	1.1	0.5	0.4	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.6	
6.5	0.5	0.5	1.2	1.2	0.7	0.8	1.2	1.2	1.0	0.9	
7.0	1.1	0.9	1.4	1.4	1.1	0.9	1.2	1.3	1.1	1.05	
7.5	-	-	1.5	1.6	1.3	1.2	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.2	
8.0	-	-	1.6	1.7	-	-	1.6	1.7	1.4	1.3	
8.5	-	-	1.8	1.8	-	-	1.7	1.7	1.5	1.4	
9.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.9	1.9	-	-	

The general reaction leading to the release of protons may be represented as follows :

From Table 1(a) it is evident that at pH 7.0 approximately one COOH group has been titrated, similarly at pH 7.5, two, at pH 8.0, approximately three and at pH 9.0 two phenolic hydroxyl groups have been titrated in addition to the three COOH groups.

Data in Table 1(b) indicate that the number of protons released per mole of metal added is approximately one in all the cases up to pH 7.5. With further increase in pH there is gradual release of proton leading to the maximum value of two approximately at pH 9.0. Thus from the observed proton release data and the theoretical reaction it may be said that possibility exists for the formation of chelate type complexes between HA and polyvalent metal cations. This also corroborates the views of Schmitzer¹³.

Magnetic properties

The magnetic moment data of different metal-HA complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE-2

MAGNETIC MOMENTS FOR VARIOUS METAL-HA COMPLEXES (IN BOHR MAGNETONS) AT 27°

Complexes	Observed moments
V ⁺⁴ - HA	1.8
Cu ⁺² - HA	2.0
Fe ⁺² - HA	5.4
Ti ⁺⁴ - HA	1.7
Mo ⁺⁶ - HA	1.75
Al ⁺³ - HA	2.3

From the magnetic moments obtained above and on comparison of the same with standard values for these metal ions as such it may be said that the

observed values are slightly higher. This may be explained as due to the fact that the electric fields of the molecules surrounding the metal ions in its compounds restrict the orbital motion of the electrons and hence the orbital moments are partially quenched. The values of magnetic moments obtained in cases of V^{+4} , Cu^{+2} , Ti^{+4} , Mo^{+6} and Al^{+3} complexes indicate the presence of just one unpaired electrons. The high value of magnetic moment in case of Fe^{+2} complex can be accounted for low lying d levels of tetrahedrally coordinated Fe^{+2} ion when there is only a small second order orbital contribution to the magnetic moment⁹. Moreover, from the positive values of magnetic susceptibility data in case of Mo^{+6} , V^{+4} , Ti^{+4} , Fe^{+2} and Al^{+3} complexes it may be inferred that the metal ions are paramagnetic in the chelates. In case of Cu^{+2} complex however the susceptibility data is negative indicating diamagnetic nature of the metal ion in the chelate. One possibility for this is that the pairs of Cu^{+2} ions are held close together usually by carboxylate ions as a result of which the spins of the two Cu^{+2} ions are so strongly coupled that the dimer is diamagnetic.

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